

How to create a README for your data publication in Zenodo

If you intend to submit a manuscript to a scientific journal, many journals now require compliance with their research data guidelines. An example of such guidelines can be found on the Elsevier publisher's website (<https://www.elsevier.com/authors/tools-and-resources/research-data/data-guidelines>). It is crucial to carefully read and follow the submission guidelines provided by the journal. Despite variations, most journals share a similar overall procedure, as indicated in the aforementioned URL. A common requirement among journals is the storage of both primary data and metadata in a data repository.

While our “Guideline for publishing data on Zenodo” and the accompanying video in openBIS describe how to use Zenodo as a data repository, here we provide a guideline how to prepare a README file that is uploaded to Zenodo along with the data.

You can find this exemplary README file as a template in openBIS. It is based on a rather generalized format which is applicable to research data from all research areas and can serve as a good starting point for your data publication.

The main purpose of the README file is to provide technical documentation about your uploaded files and their formats. Standardized file formats such as TIFF or JPEG have well-documented structures. In contrast, CSV, TXT, XLS don't inherently provide information about how and what data is stored. If you are addressing this situation by adding a header with metadata and data processing instructions (format specification, software, etc.) to your TXT file, we recommend that you also state this in the README file.

- A. Before writing a README file, consider the following steps: Gather all the data acquired during your project, whether conducted individually or in collaboration, that is intended for publication. This includes not only processed data, such as figures and charts, but also raw data and information related to the instruments and software tools used. Considering that some raw data can be quite large, surpassing 1 TB in size, it becomes impractical to store them directly in a data repository due to upload limitations (e.g., Zenodo's total file size limit per publication record is 50 GB). In this context, researchers have the flexibility to decide what data, whether raw or processed, they want to share or demonstrate, akin to the supporting information submitted with traditional publications.
- B. Once all data, both raw and processed, along with instrument and software information, have been collected, the next consideration is how to organize the data for publication. One approach, which we highly recommend, is to utilize a folder structure (e.g., Folder 1: Instrument/setup information, Folder 2: Software Tools, Folder 3: Experiments [Folder 3a: Raw Data, Folder 3b: Results], etc.) to accommodate all the data. It is advisable to utilize a pre-developed project folder structure if available.

With the data ready for publication and already organized, the next steps are the same for each of the research areas. If a researcher has worked on both synthesis and analysis (characterization) projects, they can integrate guidelines for both categories into one or more README files.

Template for a README file

The following description is exemplified by a synthesis project. However, this approach to creating a README file is independent of the research area and is applicable to e.g., simulation or software projects as well.

Synthesis projects typically consist of several categories, including samples (your own pre-samples), materials (e.g., chemicals), the synthesis protocol (describing how the sample was synthesized), and possibly some analysis or instrument tools. These categories should be adequately covered in the README file. One (recommended) option is to establish a folder structure (as mentioned above) with designated folders such as "Samples" and "Materials/Chemicals". If this approach is chosen, it can be incorporated into the corresponding template.

1. This section should encompass all essential general information, such as the title of your project or manuscript, along with the date when all the data were compiled. Additionally, for the convenience of future readers or reviewers, it would be beneficial to provide a summary detailing where specific data can be found or what data were used. This description can be highly personalized and tailored to your research area.
2. This section should present the overall structure of your ZIP file, which aligns with [Step A](#).
3. As illustrated in the example above, each folder (or structure item) should contain clear information about the data it encompasses and its intended purpose.

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## NAME of the project/manuscript

This data publication is based on the metadata and data sets underlying the manuscript [NAME]

** The data collected are from July 2023.**

** This file contains information about the datasets used, [MENTIONING OF YOUR DATA (e.g., the processed and raw data of the figures, etc.
in the manuscript, the visualization/setup tools, etc.)

## Content and source of the folders: [PLEASE KEEP IN MIND, THE FOLLOWING STRUCTURE IS JUST AN EXAMPLE; IF YOU HAVE NO PROCESSED DATA, YOU
MIGHT SKIP 5.]

1.'Synthesis protocol': [OF COURSE YOU CAN ALSO MERGE THE INFORMATION INTO ONE FILE]
  * Contains the synthesis protocol for nanoparticle XY with ... *
  * Contains the synthesis protocol for nanoparticle BV with ... *

2.'Materials/Chemicals': [OF COURSE YOU CAN ALSO MERGE THE INFORMATION INTO ONE FILE]
  * Contains all information about the used chemicals during the synthesis procedures of nanoparticle XY *
  * Contains all information about the used chemicals during the synthesis procedures of nanoparticle BV *

3.'Samples information': [OF COURSE YOU CAN ALSO MERGE THE INFORMATION INTO ONE FILE]
  * Contains the characterization/pore-analysis/... information on nanoparticle XY.
  * Contains the characterization/pore-analysis/... information on nanoparticle BV.

4.'Experimental raw data': [HERE, IT IS UP TO YOU IF YOU WANT TO CLUSTER RAW DATA ACCORDING TO THE NANOPARTICLE OR SOMETHING ELSE]
  * Contains the raw data of the ... [UVvis spectrum/NMR data/DLS data/...] for nanoparticle XY. These data are gathered in subfolder [NAME
e.g. Nanoparticle XY, etc.]. The formatting specifications are stated in the files' headers. *
  * Contains the raw data of the ... [UVvis spectrum/NMR data/DLS data/...] for nanoparticle BV. These data are gathered in subfolder [NAME
e.g. Nanoparticle BV, etc.]. The formatting specifications are stated in the files' headers. *
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4. This section should contain descriptions and relevant information about each data or data set stored in the respective folders.
5. For instance, consider the first exemplary folder named "synthesis protocol", which includes a DOCX file documenting the complete synthetic procedure of the developed samples. If you are not sure how to describe your data or data set, you can utilize a general protocol, similar to what would typically be included in the supporting information of a publication. This approach can also be applied to instrumentation details; just think about how you would describe them in the "Instrumentation" or "Method" section of your manuscript.

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## Content and source of the files for Folder 'Synthesis protocol': [THE NEXT PHRASES ARE ONLY EXAMPLES AND CAN BE ADJUSTED ACCORDINGLY] 4
1. 'Synthesis Protocol of all developed nanoparticles.docx'
  * Contains the synthesis protocol for nanoparticles XY, BV, ... as docx.file. This can also be found in the Supporting Information S1-3 *
  * ... *

## Content and source of the files for Folder 'Materials/Chemicals': [THE NEXT PHRASES ARE ONLY EXAMPLES AND CAN BE ADJUSTED ACCORDINGLY]
1. 'Material list Nanoparticle.docx'
  * Contains a list of materials for the synthesis procedures for nanoparticles XY, BV, ... as docx.file. This can also be found in the
  Materials part of the main manuscript. *
2. 'Material list Analysis.docx'
  * Contains a list of materials for the analyses of nanoparticles XY, BV, ... as docx.file. This can also be found in the Materials part
  of the main manuscript. *
[...] 5

## Content and source of the files for Folder 'Experimental raw data': [THE NEXT PHRASES ARE ONLY EXAMPLES AND CAN BE ADJUSTED ACCORDINGLY]
1. 'UVvis-spectrum_XY.ascii'
  * Contains the raw data of 'Figure 1. Absorption spectrum of nanoparticle XY in water/ethanol.' as .ascii file. The data is stored row-
  wise and can be opened with a standard text editor. The setup information can be found in the 'Instrumentation' folder/header of the
  file/... *
2. 'UVvis-spectrum_BV.ascii'
  * Contains the raw data of 'Figure 2. Absorption spectrum of nanoparticle BV in water/ethanol' as .ascii file. The data is stored column-
  wise can be opened with a standard text editor. The setup information can be found in the 'Instrumentation' folder/header of the file/...
  . *
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Once your data have been appropriately described, you are ready to submitting them to a data repository to obtain a DOI for your data or data sets, which can then be added to your manuscript. For the latter, please refer to our “Guideline for publishing data on Zenodo”.